

Mass distribution in satellite and planetary systems (modeling and demonstrating).

Introduction

There are few apparent specificities of celestial bodies' placement within natural orbital systems. It is ought to innumerate these basic observable facts (separate phenomena) that further on we'll try to interpret as associated. Firstly, the equatorial plane is the obligatory discoid structure that organizes the natural orbital system (satellite or planetary). Secondly, the location of the most massive orbiting objects is quite definite on equatorial planes of multi-satellite or multi-planetary systems. Thirdly, the prograde orbiting takes place within close-in orbits and moderately distant orbits; the retrograde orbiting appears mostly within outer orbits.

Methods and modeling

The interpretation of the observing regularities by means of mathematical model suggests the process of simulation based on the initial set of relationships. Here the initial relationships of the model are assembled as axiomatic statement from where we start.

In 3D isotropic space: there is the 2D one-sided isotropic subspace in which the two physical categories are mapped: 1) the mass (in terms of the geometry of gravitating object and in terms of the dust cloud); 2) the accelerated curvilinear motion (in terms of vector algebra of orbiting).

The mass. From the point of view of gravitation we always deal with the two types of mass organization – compact and dissipated. The compact type, - on an astronomical scale, - is the one that reveals the isotropy of 3D space by taking form of sphere. The dissipated type (in other words, dust cloud) reveals the isotropy of 3D space due to the concept of the volume, approximately globe-shaped either, but lacking the surface as such and, consequently, lacking the definite shape of it. Apropos, the dissipated mass does not relate to gravitating objects and is not considered in GTR.

The mapping of the mass of a ball onto the 2D space means the representation of the surface of sphere to the plane with the subsequent bijection of the volume of sphere on it; the information about the density will permit to transform the volumetric units to the mass. Taking into consideration the isotropy of 2D space we may accept the azimuth unfolding of spherical

surface on a plane because it is the optimal way to conserve isotropy of 3D space within isotropy of 2D subspace (Fig.1).

In contrast, the mapping of the dust cloud on the plane can hardly conserve the signs of isotropy of 3D space as far as any certain form of the cloud is rejected. Even if the cloud tends to be spheroid (again because of 3D isotropy) we lack the opportunity to speak about the surface of it as a skin. Hence, the whole volume of a cloud must be represented as a square: the transformation equalizes the volume and the surface. The mapping on the plane of such a surface must express only the essential 2D isotropy of the 2D space, i.e. the above mentioned square must take the form of a circle or a round-like spot. The volume of the cloud will be bijectively reflected to this round square and, - in case the density of dust cloud is known, - to the mass.

As far as 2D subspace (the acceptor of the two above mappings) is situated inside of 3D space (3D Euclidean space) we may place the azimuth unfolding of sphere (the compact type of mass) on the one side of the 2D space and the round spot of homogeneous structure (the dust type of mass) on the other side of 2D space. Since 2D space is one-sided space (Mobius strip) the both mappings will be superimposed. Henceforth, speculations will concern the object with mixed characteristics. The mass is distributed on the plane as the azimuth unfolding of sphere with longitudinal (meridian) difference of the widths of the petal (lobe) at the each latitude. But also the abstract mass is dissipated as a disk with homogeneous distribution of matter. So we may combine the picture with differences of mass distribution with the picture of uniform scattering of mass. For example, the width of the petal at the latitude L_1 is A and the length of L_1 is X (this length includes petal widths, all equal to A , and intermediate voids of some constant widths); the average mass-distribution along the latitude L_1 is $f(A,X)$; for the latitude L_2 the mass-distribution along L_2 (i.e. the average amount of the mass) is different and equal to $f(B,Y)$, where B is the width of petal at L_2 and Y is the length of L_2 . The averaging is conceivable as some form of dissipation of the matter along the latitudes: the matter concentrated in petals is dissipating along the latitudinal ring of conditional width. Consequently, the main characteristic of mass distribution now will be the concentration of matter throughout the latitudinal ring: the units of mass per the unit of square of latitudinal ring (of some conditional width). Hence, the highest concentration will be observed in the ring where the petals connect each other; obviously, concentration decreases when comparing the concentric rings - either in the direction towards the centre or towards the periphery (Fig.1). It is pertinent to interpret the difference of concentration as the affinity to frame "the massiveness" of future compact spheroids (planets or satellites).

Curvilinear closed motion. Curvilinear motion is the accelerated motion in all cases. Our model comprises the closed trajectories because it is the basic variant of curvilinear motion in astronomy: it is about orbiting. This limitation, possibly, is symmetrical to previous one concerning the fact that the most common 3D form of mass in cosmic relationships is a spheroid. We look for the bonds between the definite shape of mass and the definite version of curvilinear motion – both typical for astronomical scale. We do not searching the bonds between mass itself and any motion in non-inertial reference frame.

The mapping of curvilinear closed motion upon the 2D space sets up the plane framed of concentric orbits. The plane is already divided to latitudinal zones featuring different concentration of matter due to the azimuth unfolding of sphere mapped to it. The orbiting objects, being the product of evolution of dissipated matter into the compact form, represent now the different concentrations of matter (specific to the each latitude) as variation of massiveness of orbiting objects.

As far as the whole orbiting system is based on the integral pattern of azimuth unfolding of sphere it is pertinent to consider that the directions of rotations will be aggregated. The initial choice of the direction of rotation may only depend on the spin of the central gravitating object. If so, we may introduce the concept of prograde orbiting.

According to the construction of the model (see above the axiomatics) we speak about the mapping of closed curvilinear motion upon the 2D space and we artificially place all orbits on the same plane. So we encounter with specific plane of rotation where the orbits - or the concentric rings (the substance yet remains as a dust) - are moving separately but the direction of rotation is general.

Circular motion has the construction of the pair of polar vectors and the axial vector of angular rate (perpendicular to the rotation). Despite the different orbiting velocities we may generalize the orbiting system as the common plane of rotation with the common axial vector (concerning its rotation direction). It results in organizing the general 3D coordinate system where the plane of rotation coincides with the one of orthogonal planes of coordinate system. Then the axial vector is considered a pseudo vector: mirror reflection of coordinate system (by means of changing the right system to left one, or by means the inversion from top to bottom) will generate the opposite direction of pseudo vector and the reverse rotation of it will appears when looking from the opposite side of 2D space. Now the axiomatic condition of the model takes effect: 2D space is one-sided space (let's imagine plane circle with thin handle twisted in a way of Mobius stripe). As a consequence, simultaneous rotation in opposite directions of axial

vector will be observed when looking from each surface of such a plane. If we could reckon the unidirectional orbiting of all objects participating in mass distribution – then the opposite direction of axial vector rotation ought to be associated with orbiting of the objects which does not participate in mass distribution. The latter may be only the objects from somewhere at outer orbits. In other words, the phenomenon of retrograde orbiting can be observed beyond the limitations denoted by the external tips of the petals, i.e. at outer orbits (probably alternating with the remnants of prograde orbiting).

Again about the mass. Azimuth unfolding of spherical surface is shown at Fig.1. Here we see the pattern composed of ten petals where the each petal is inserted into one of the ten imaginary sectors.

Fig.1 Ten-petal azimuth pattern of the unfolded spherical surface.

The ring-like zone, packed totally with the material of petals (i.e. where the petals connect each other), is not located in the center of the pattern and not at the equatorial region.

Here, at Fig.1, the example is shown: the pattern composed of ten petals which are relatively slim. The dependence between the curvature of the arc of the petal and the number of petals is quite obvious, i.e. the ring-like zone of connections may shift due to the number of petals. Nevertheless, diapason of shifts is restricted – the central void spot never disappears into the dot when the number of petals is diminishing and zone of connections of petals never reaches the equator when the number of petals increases.

As stated above the mass distribution depends on the position of concentric latitudinal ring which demonstrates the certain concentration of matter (units of mass per the unit of square of the latitudinal ring of some conditional width). The discoid plane with such mass distribution can be associated with equatorial plane of planetary or satellite system. Three distinguishable zones can be revealed. There is the inner ring featuring the paucity of elements of spherical unfolding on the plane due to central divergence of the petal tips and presence of the blank spot (close-in orbits). There is the middle ring that occupies the position between the centre and equator, the position that can be compared to “the tropical parallel”. The middle ring possesses the maximum of spherical surface per the unit of planar surface (moderately close orbits). At last we see the external zone that demonstrates the peripheral divergence of petals; this zone specifies the decrease of presence of spherical unfolded surface on the planar surface, i.e. we see the decrease of such a proportion with distance (outer orbits). Approximate assessment of the bond between the distance (from the center of equatorial plate up to the orbit of the celestial body) and the massiveness of celestial body can be advanced in view of simple mathematizing.

Let’s revisit the azimuth pattern of the surface of a sphere composed of ten petals (Fig.1) and note that the petals are wedged into the respective sectors (the circle is divided into ten sectors either). The petal turns out to be jammed when the certain width of the petal coincides with the certain sector width, so the critical point ought to be formalized. The structural element of azimuth unfolded surface of sphere should be isolated (now it is the petal inside the sector) and half-petal divided lengthwise should be presented as a segment of the virtual circle of radius R (Fig.2).

Fig. 2 The structural element of azimuth petal model - the petal wedged in the sector. The half-petal (petal divided lengthwise) can be seen as a segment of some circle of radius R (h is the height of the segment). Sections AB (the tangent) and AD (the secant) are drawn from one point outside the circle.

It is easy to discern the Tangent Secant Theorem here: $AB^2 = AD \times AC$. Getting such a tool we may analyze more informative astronomical resources for interpretation the spacing nearby points B , C and D in respect of dependence “the mass of orbiting object – the distance from the main gravitating object”. The bond is quite relative because the referring point is the place where the total filling of the unit of plain with elements of unfolded sphere is observing (the orbits with maximal mass loading). Such a place is located within point B ; the masses and distances are individual for each planet or satellite system.

Astronomical evidence: exoplanet systems

Exoplanet systems are really planar that permits us to associate such systems with discoid plane; hence, we may use the azimuth unfolding of spherical surface as a cliché for comparison to the observed facts of mass distribution. Maximum that we can afford is the general view on the difference between circumcentral zone (blank spot with inner tips of petals) and intermediate zone (where the petals connect each other) (Fig.1). What are the well-known facts about exoplanet distribution? Maximal number of discovered exoplanets is located relatively near the host star; the fact concerns the orbits either of massive planets or of not very massive (Fig.3).

Fig.3 The distribution of exoplanets in dependence of periods and masses.

1 M_E = 0.003 Jupiter's mass; vertical line divides gas giants and brown dwarfs [1].

Such distribution of exoplanets corresponds to the affinity of exoplanet's orbits to the ring where the petals connect each other, i.e. where the maximal concentration of unfolded spherical surface per the unit of planar surface takes place. Consequently, the preferable habitation of the planets is situated not far from the host star but is not very close to.

Second phenomenon is the dearth of massive planets at close-in orbits. The observations reveal the absence of high mass planets beyond 1 AU and the paucity of high mass planets within 1 AU (Fig.4).

Fig.4 The dearth of massive planets orbiting close in to the host stars [2].

The inner part of the azimuth unfolding of spherical surface consists of the central blank spot and small triangular squares of petal tips presenting moderate overall concentration of substance per unit of planar surface. It is appropriate for the relatively weak planet formation at close-in orbits.

Astronomical evidence: gas giants' satellite systems

The appearance of satellite with retrograde orbiting should be interpreted as the border of applicability of petal model – the point D denotes the external tip of the petal. All satellites located closer to the central gravitating object demonstrate prograde orbiting and are involved in mass distribution according to azimuth unfolding of spherical surface; Neptune seems to be the exception but it is embedded into some dynamics observing in accordance with the spacial arrangement of gas giants in Solar system. Thus, structuralized mass distribution exists in the range between the nearest satellite with prograde orbiting (its semi-major axis is equal to AC) and the nearest satellite with retrograde orbiting (its semi-major axis is equal to AD). The distance denotes the length of full secant AD which can be computed by means of the values of AB and AC due to the Tangent Secant Theorem.

Jupiter. The nearest satellite's semi-major axis (ax) is 128000 km. The two most massive satellites located next to each other are: Ganimede with diameter (d) 5262 km, ax 1070412 km and Callisto (d 4821 km, ax 1882709 km). The nearest satellite with retrograde orbiting is Euporie: ax **19265800** km, d 2 km, i (inclination) 146°. Calculation due to the Tangent Secant Theorem, while using of the mean value of two semi-major axes (Ganimede, Callisto), results in **17033066** km. The value can be approximated to the ax Euporie with deficit **-11.6%**. The applicability of the petal model is spread to the level of the nearest satellite with retrograde orbiting (Euporie) but Jupiter satellite system is tailed away to 30 mln.km (in terms of ax) being absolutely homogenous in respect of the direction of orbiting (totally retrograde orbiting, no satellites with prograde orbiting) and being represented mostly by satellites of small diameters (together with several middle-sized ones).

Saturn. The nearest satellite: ax 117000. The satellite of eminent massiveness (Titan): d 5150 km, ax 1221900 km. The nearest satellite with retrograde orbiting: Phoebe (ax **12929400** km, d 240 km, i 175°). Calculation due to the Tangent Secant Theorem results in **12761022** km approximated to the ax Phoebe with deficit of **-1.3%** only. Phoebe indicates the level of external tips of petals, i.e. the completion of applicability of the model which pretends to explain mass distribution due to unfolded spherical surface. The rest of Saturn satellite system (located farther than Phoebe; the whole equatorial plane extends up to 27 mln.km) consists of the two parts. The first one is the mixture of small and middle-sized satellites orbiting in prograde and retrograde directions and the second one (18 mln.km and farther) is homogenous: a lot of small satellites with retrograde orbiting.

Uranus. The nearest satellite: ax 49800 km. The two most massive adjacent satellites: Titania (d 1577 km, ax 436282 km) and Oberon (d 1523, ax 583449 km). The nearest satellite with retrograde orbiting: Francisco (ax **4275700** km, d 22 km, i 147°). Calculation due to the Tangent Secant Theorem and usage of the mean value of two semi-major axes (Titania, Oberon) results in **5222194** km; here we observe the excess **+22%**, i.e. we need to reduce the calculated value by 22% in order to reach the really observed. The petal model covers Uranium's satellite system up to Francisco but equatorial disc extends farther (21 mln km) in the form of homogenous zone of medium-sized satellites with retrograde orbiting, excepting the only one, Margarita (ax 14345000, d 11, i 52°).

The conclusion ensuing from these three variants (Jupiter, Saturn and Uranium) is the following: the appearance of retrograde orbiting indicates the bond between the direction of rotation of central gravitating object and the end of structuring of satellite system in the aspect of mass distribution. Besides, we may notice, firstly, the dynamics of the error (difference

compared to factual value, in percent): **-11.6%**, **-1.3%**, **+22%**; secondly, the vast region of outer orbits (of the each of these gas giant) is represented almost totally by retrograde orbiting objects (relatively small in sizes). Thirdly, in case of Uranus, the gap appears between the most massive satellites, Titania and Oberon (with prograde orbiting, of course), and the nearest satellite with retrograde orbiting; the phenomenon refers to **+22%** and to the extension of two successions: Saturn has 5 satellites between (**-1.3%**,) and Jupiter has 10 satellites between (**-11.6%**).

Neptune. The nearest satellite: ax 48224 km. The satellite of eminent massiveness and, - at the same time, - the nearest satellite with retrograde orbiting is Triton: d 2705 km, ax 354759 km, i 157°. At a glance: placement of moons does not fit the previous formula because Triton is the most massive satellite and, at the same time, the nearest to Neptune satellite with retrograde orbiting. Triton is followed by heterogeneous zone of prograde and retrograde orbiting satellites.

When looking at the succession of mistakes (-11.6% -1.3% +22%) we may extrapolate the case of Neptune the following way. The orbit of the nearest retrograde satellite should be shifted in the direction toward the most massive one (the latter ostensibly demonstrating the prograde orbiting). The shift should be more prominent than in case of Uranus and, respectively, the gap analogous to Uranus' one (between the most massive prograde satellite and the nearest retrograde satellite) should be collapsed; consequently, we may interpret the observation as some critical point. The possibility to calculate the secant AD is excluded. The phenomenon of confluence of such characteristics like “the most massive” and “the nearest retrograde” on the example of Triton permits us to avoid the version with capture of this satellite by Neptune and, hence, permits to presume the placement of satellites in Neptune's system as the part of some more general system (we are not aware of).

Astronomical evidence: the Solar system

Semi-major axis of Jupiter is taken as AB (5.2 AU), semi-major axis of Mercury is taken as AC (0.38 AU) and the calculated value of AD will correspond to the distance from the centre up to external tips of the petals, i.e. to the periphery of Solar system where we expect to find the transmission from the prograde orbiting to the total retrograde orbiting (like in case of Jupiter, Saturn or Uranus). Thus, $(5.2)^2/0.38 = 71.2$ AU. The value slightly exceeds the farther border of Kuiper belt - 55 AU from the Sun. The nearest to the Sun asteroid with retrograde orbiting is located in Kuiper belt quite nearer: 2008YB3 (d 67 km, ax **11.6** AU, i 105°). The result is not sufficient, but keeping in mind the relative integrity of Kuiper belt and Scattered disc we may notice the absence of peripheral region with totally retrograde orbiting of asteroids. Moreover,

there are not too many ones of the kind among the prevailing number of asteroids with prograde orbiting.

Nevertheless, the presence of asteroids with retrograde orbits at the periphery of Solar system (not sporadic but systematical event anyway) permits us to distinguish the main region of their location. Now the doubtful game with averaging begins. If we omit the faraway retrograde orbiting asteroids like 2015BZ509 (ax 769 AU, i 163°) or 2005VX3 (ax 1580 AU, i 112°), - and then enumerate almost all of the rest using the available information, - the list comprises retrograde asteroids in the range from 10 AU to 200 AU:

2008YB3 – ax 11.6 AU, i 105°

2011MM4 – ax 21.1 AU, i 101°

2011KT19 – ax 35.6 AU, i 110°

2008KV42 – ax 45.5 AU, i 104°

2016NM56 – ax 73.3 AU, i 144°

2013LU28 – ax 180.9 AU, i 125°

2013BL76 – ax 187.6 AU, i 99°

The mean value of **79.4** AU is accompanied by significant standard deviation (68.8 AU). Median value falls on 45.5 AU which shows the distance almost half nearer to the Sun. If we add to the list the two above mentioned faraway asteroids the median value raises up to 73.3 AU.

The calculations are hardly convincing with the exception of the fact ensuing: the appearance of retrograde orbiting objects occurs in peripheral parts of petals (not exactly at the tips) being mixed with still prevailing amount of prograde orbiting objects. It possibly means that in contrast to cases with Jupiter, Saturn and Uranus the systems of another level (planetary systems) do not strictly separate rotations of the two axial vectors. The region is dispersed and the family of the objects with retrograde orbiting is not very representative comparing to the case of multi-satellite systems of gas giants.

Summarizing

The following aspect may complete the findings with focus on evolution of planetary and satellite systems. One-sided 2D space accepts the mapping of spherical geometry and of the

indistinct form of the dust cloud. The transition to mass-distribution proposes the mixture of structural characteristics of the azimuth unfolding mapping of spherical surface on 2D space and the dissipation of the stuff as a discoid mapping of dust cloud on 2D space (resulting in organization of meridian difference and parallel equalizing). In the model it is only the averaging technique necessary for further presenting of the obtained mass as an object (as the carrier of this mass – the planet or the satellite). But at early period of evolution of rotational systems it is just the real dust cloud may be organized – with regard to mass-distribution - according to the azimuth unfolding mapping of spherical surface (in case the cloud comes across with the large gravitating object with rotation).

References

1/// <http://exoplanet.eu>

2/// Geoffrey Marcy, R. Paul Butler, Debra Fischer, Steven Vogt, Jason T. Wright, Chris G. Tinney and Hugh R. A. Jones Observed Properties of Exoplanets: Masses, Orbits, and Metallicities Progress of Theoretical Physics Supplement No. 158, 2005.